

Socio-technical factors generating social debt

Table 2: Collaboration and Social Structure factor.

Id	Cause and Primary studies
CSF1	Unresolved conflicts between team members that deteriorate trust [PS1, PS2, PS5, PS21, PS26, PS27, PS33, PS39, PS40, PS41, PS43, PS45].
CSF2	Lack of transparency in knowledge sharing [PS2, PS6, PS7, PS9, PS21, PS22, PS27, PS32, PS33, PS38–PS41, PS43, PS45].
CSF3	Dominant participation by individuals with strong personalities [PS1, PS27, PS33, PS39, PS43].
CSF4	Absence of social ties between developers working on shared tasks [PS1, PS2, PS6, PS9, PS27, PS33, PS37, PS43, PS45].
CSF5	Poor collaboration due to a lack of psychological safety and inclusive leadership that fosters active participation [PS1, PS2, PS26, PS27, PS33, PS39].
CSF6	“Lone wolf” behavior, exemplified by developers who focus solely on their own code without contributing to integration efforts [PS6, PS7, PS27, PS33, PS38, PS39, PS43, PS45].
CSF7	Presence of fragmented and inflexible social structures [PS6, PS7, PS9, PS21, PS24, PS27, PS32, PS33, PS34, PS38–PS41, PS43, PS44].
CSF8	Fragmented social networks among developers that hinder team cohesion [PS6, PS9, PS23, PS27, PS32, PS33, PS34, PS38, PS39, PS43–PS45].
CSF9	Limited collaboration resulting from misalignment between project governance and product vision [PS2, PS21, PS27, PS33, PS39, PS40, PS41, PS45].
CSF10	Poorly defined architectural roles and inequitable distribution of responsibilities [PS7, PS27, PS33, PS38, PS39, PS40, PS41, PS45].
CSF11	Homogeneous organizational structures that promote rigid social patterns and short-term thinking [PS9, PS27, PS33, PS39].
CSF12	Fragile structures vulnerable to staff turnover and poor scalability [PS1, PS6, PS24, PS27, PS32, PS39, PS45].
CSF13	Incorrect structural decisions impacting team coordination [PS7, PS9, PS21, PS27, PS33, PS37, PS39, PS40, PS41, PS43, PS45].
CSF14	Presence of antisocial behaviors within the team [PS2, PS9, PS27, PS33, PS39].
CSF15	Existence of organizational anti-patterns such as fear, isolation, and excessive bureaucracy [PS1, PS6, PS23, PS27, PS32, PS38, PS39, PS45].

Acronyms used: Collaboration and Social Structure factor (CSF).